

Magnetic and Impedance Spectroscopy Studies in Mg Doped Barium Hexaferrite

PratapBehera and S. Ravi*

Department of Physics, Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati, Guwahati – 781039

*Corresponding author Email: sravi@iitg.ernet.in, Contact no. (0361-258-2707)

Abstract

Y-type hexaferrites have attracted an extensive research interest due to their potential applications in electronic and microwave devices [1-2]. Polycrystalline Mg-doped $\text{Ba}_2(\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Mg}_x)_2\text{Fe}_{12}\text{O}_{22}$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1$) samples are found to be in single phase form and their crystal structure, magnetic and dielectric properties are studied. The saturation magnetization (M_s) values are found to decrease from 27 emu/g for $x = 0$ to 20 emu/g for $x = 1$ samples. Similarly the coercivity (H_c) values are found to decrease with increase in Mg concentration. The temperature dependence magnetization measurement shows that the Curie temperature decreases from 613K for $x=0$ to 535K for $x = 1$. Impedance spectroscopy measurements at different temperatures exhibit relaxation peaks due to grains and grain boundaries contributions. The analysis of ac conductivity data in terms of Jonscher power law suggests that the underlying conduction mechanism is controlled by small polaron hopping. The activation energy for conduction is found to decrease with Mg doping from 0.77eV for $x = 0$ to 0.23eV for $x = 1$. The detailed analysis of magnetic and impedance spectroscopy studies and the underlying physical mechanism would be presented.

Keywords: Mg doped Barium Hexaferrite, ac impedance spectroscopy, small polaron hopping,

References

1. H. Khanduri et al. J. Appl. Phys. 112 (2012) 073903.
2. S. H. Chun et al. Phys. Rev. Lett. 104, (2010) 037204.